

Chemical activation of Vulcan[®] XC72R to be used as support for NiNbPtRu catalysts in PEM fuel cells

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Abstract: Carbon supports are widely used as electro-catalyst supports in low-temperature fuel cells. As the structure and physical properties of these supports have an influence on their properties, the aim is to find a simple method to obtain supports with suitable porosity, good conductivity and stable in fuel cell environment. In this work, a method for chemical activation of Vulcan XC72R has been developed to obtain a support for Ni₅₉Nb₄₀Pt_{0.6}Ru_{0.4} catalysts in MEAs. With fixed work conditions such as carbon/KOH ratio, N₂ flow, heating rate, time and treatment temperature as a starting point, different washing procedures to remove the Potassium compounds for the resulting material have been devised. Results show that the activation treatment improves the behavior of the supports and the importance of the washing method on the removal of the alkaline compounds. Samples washed using HCl and HNO₃ solutions (VKCl and VKN) show much better results than those that were solely washed using deionized water (VKOH). This could be explained by the fact that Potassium compounds with low solubility in water could be blocking the access to some of the created porosity and removal could be improved in the presence on an acid solution.

1. Introduction

Because of the awareness that has built up about the environmental consequences of today's energy model, clean electricity production has taken a high relevance during these last years. Hydrogen fuel cells belong to the group of environmentally friendly technologies as they are able to produce electricity by electrochemical conversion of hydrogen and oxygen into water. Polymer electrolyte membrane fuel cells (PEMFCs) are low temperature fuel cells with great potential for transportation and portable purposes [1]. Carbon supported platinum or platinum alloys are used as anode and cathode catalyst in these fuel cells.

Porous carbon materials are excellent candidates for catalyst supports. In recent years, a wide variety of porous carbon materials have been developed to this end: physical supports such as mesostructured carbon materials [2e4], carbon nanotubes [5,6], and graphitic carbon nanofibers [7] or nanocomposite materials with Pt active sites [8e10]. While these carbon-supported catalysts have shown enhanced catalytic activities, practical application of these carbons is limited because of the complexity and cost of production. In this work, the carbon/catalyst system will consist on a blend or mixture of an amorphous catalyst alloy and a carbon powder.

Good conductive properties, low cost, low ash content, high chemical and electrochemical stability and availability make carbon blacks a good option. Because of this, Vulcan XC72R is one of the most commonly used carbon blacks as an electrocatalyst support [11e14]. Vulcan is an oil-furnace carbon black material obtained by feeding the starting material into a furnace and burning it at about 1400 C with a limited amount of oxygen present.

Generally, carbon blacks must be treated before its use as a catalyst support. The objective of this treatment is to modify its pore structure (to eliminate very small micropores that are not accessible to the electrolyte [15]) or to change the surface chemistry through the creation of oxidized species such as carboxylic groups, phenolic, or etheric groups. In either case, the purpose is to obtain a better dispersion of the catalyst on the surface of the support and to improve the accessibility of the reactives to the active sites.

There are two main types of processes to produce activated carbons: physical activation and chemical activation. In the case of physical activation, the precursor suffers a carbonization process followed by a gasification of the remaining char or the precursor is exposed to an oxidizing atmosphere such as CO₂ or steam at high temperatures. In both cases, the process eliminates the most reactive carbon atoms in the structure creating new porosity. In the case of chemical activation, the precursor is mixed with a certain chemical substance and pyrolyzed. As result of this process, a carbon with a more ordered structure will be obtained and, once the activating agents are removed, a more developed pore structure. One of the most popular activating agents to produce active carbons is KOH. During the chemical activation, the washing step can be a determining factor because the incorporation of impurities derived from the activating agent may affect the properties of the resulting activated carbon [16].

In this work, different procedures have been used to wash the carbon black after activation and these resulting carbons have been tested to observe the effect of this process on the performance of an MEA in a PEM single cell. For better understanding of the behavior of the different carbon supports, they have been characterized by Nitrogen Adsorption, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) and Fourier Transform Infra Red spectra (FT-IR).

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemical activation of Vulcan XC-72R

For this work, a commercial carbon black Vulcan XC-72R (Cabot) was chosen as a precursor for the activated carbon. Chemical activation with KOH was carried out mixing mechanically the carbon black and KOH on the ratio of activating agent/precursor of 1/1 (w/w). The resulting mixture was carbonized in a horizontal tube furnace with a heating rate of 20 K min⁻¹ up to 1023 K in a nitrogen flow of 10 L h⁻¹. Samples were kept at 1023 K for 2 h before cooling down under nitrogen.

The pyrolyzed samples were washed to remove the activating agent (or any other alkaline compound that formed during activation). For this purpose the samples were first thoroughly washed with deionized water. In the first case, once the activating agent was removed, the sample was dried at 373 K for 12 h (VKOH).

For the other two samples, once the KOH-activated carbon had been washed with water, it was washed again with a 3.8 M acid solution (VKCl when the acid used was HCl and VKN when the acid was HNO₃) and later with deionized water. Once the samples were washed, they were dried as mentioned before.

Process yields were calculated and in all cases very high yields were obtained, over 85% (including possible material loss due to the washing process).

2.2. Characterization of the carbon supports

The porous texture characterization of all samples has been evaluated by physical adsorption-desorption of N₂ at 77 K (Micromeritics, ASAP 2020). Samples were previously outgassed at 413 K for 24 h. The specific surface area was determined by the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. Micropore volumes have been calculated from the adsorption isotherms of nitrogen applying the *t*-plot method. Mesopore volume and pore size distribution were obtained applying the Barrete-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method.

SEM micrographs and chemical analysis by Energy Dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) measurements were taken at a Scanning Electron Microscopy JEOL (model JSM6400) equipped with EDX microanalysis (Oxford Link EXL II) and WDX (2 spec. JEOL).

The characterization of surface oxygen groups of the different samples was done by FTIR. The infrared studies were conducted with an FTIR system (Nicolet, Nexus 670) with a DTGS detector. Spectra were obtained at 298 K and diluted in KBr.

2.3. Electrochemical set up

The carbon supports are used to prepare catalyst inks that will be used to be applied on a Nafion 115 (DuPont, USA) solid polymer electrolyte membrane to build an MEA. Nafion 115 membranes were heated at 80 °C in a 5 wt% hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) solution (Scharlau 30%) for 1 h and rinsed with double-distilled water. Then, they were heated at 80 °C in a 1 M sulfuric acid (H₂SO₄) (95% 98%, Panreac) solution for 1 h and rinsed with double-distilled water again [17].

The catalyst inks for the anode were prepared by mixing the electro-catalysts powders, the carbon, Nafion solution, double-distilled water and ethanol. In this case, due to the size of the electrocatalyst particles, the carbon used is not technically supporting nor dispersing the catalyst, but is part of a blend and its function is to improve integration of the catalyst particles and insure a good catalyst-membrane interaction in the MEA. Details of the preparation and main characteristics of this amorphous catalyst

have been described by J. Barranco et al. [18,19]. The anode catalyst layer was prepared by mixing 40 mg cm² of electro-catalyst (Ni₅₉Nb₄₀Pt_{0.6}Ru_{0.4}), 1.5 mg of Vulcan KOH-treated carbon,

Table 1 Pore structure characteristics of carbon blacks that were studied in this work: untreated Vulcan XC-72R (V) and chemically activated Vulcan washed with water (VKOH), HCl (VKCl) and HNO₃ (VKN).

Sample	S _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹)	V _{micropore} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V _{mesopore} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)	V _{total} (cm ³ g ⁻¹)
V	248	0.067	0.49	0.55
VKOH	167	0.012	0.44	0.51
VKCl	191	0.022	0.49	0.56
VKN	198	0.020	0.54	0.60

120 mL of Nafion (Aldrich, 20 wt.%) in 2 mL ethanol (Scharlau) and 1 mL of doubled-distilled water. The cathode catalyst ink was prepared by mixing 40 mg cm² of Pt/C (20 wt.%, Alfa Aesar), 120 mL of Nafion (Aldrich, 20 wt.%) in 2 mL ethanol (Scharlau) and 1 mL doubled-distilled water. The catalyst inks were sonicated for 30 min to disperse the catalyst particles homogeneously before spraying them onto the membrane. This procedure was followed to achieve a constant Pt loading on the anode and the cathode sides. The real loading amount of Pt was calculated by weighing the catalyst ink before and after painting the MEA. The amount of Pt deposited on the anode was 0.093 mg Pt. The MEAs were hot pressed at 120 C under a pressure of 50\$10⁵ Pa for 1.5 min [20]. Finally, they were activated in HF 48% (PA, Panreac) and rinsed out with doubled distilled water. The fuel cell testing was performed using cell surfaces of 9 cm².

MEAs were prepared by bonding anode and cathode electro-catalyst layers to opposite sides of the membrane (a three layer structure) and covering the catalyst layers with a gas diffusion layer (GDL) and a backing layer. EC-CC1-060 Electrochem carbon cloth was used as the GDL.

MEAs were tested in a PEM single cell hardware where pure hydrogen (3x, Praxair) and pure oxygen (4x, Praxair) were supplied to the anode and cathode respectively. The following gas flows were used: 40 mL min⁻¹ (10⁵ Pa) for hydrogen and 20 mL min⁻¹ (0.5. 10⁵ Pa) for oxygen. All tests were performed at room temperature and 0% humidity that was achieved by-passing the humidifiers, which had been turned off. Polarization curve measurements were controlled and recorded by LabView software (National Instruments).

In order to obtain a complete picture of how the changes suffered by the Vulcan carbon during activation and its following washing process have affected its behavior, MEAs were also built using untreated Vulcan XC-72R (V) and a commercial Glassy Carbon (CV) from SigmaAldrich. As the Vulcan carbon black has a smaller particle size than the glassy carbon, the amount of Vulcan carbon used for the catalyst inks has been 10 times smaller than for the glassy carbon.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physical and chemical characterization of carbon supports

The main surface area characteristics of the carbon supports obtained in this work are shown in Table 1. The first noticeable difference between the untreated and the activated Vulcan carbon blacks is that activation has decreased the specific surface area of the carbons. Fig. 1 shows the N₂ adsorption isotherms at 77 K for the different samples. All the adsorption isotherms are of type IV, typical of

mesoporous materials with a capillary condensation step [21]. It can be observed that the porous texture of the Vulcan carbon has dramatically changed after KOH activation.

Fig. 1 e Nitrogen adsorption/desorption isotherms for Vulcan XC-72R carbon black (a) and the activated Vulcan carbon black supports: VKOH (b), VKCl (c) and VKN (d).

The activated Vulcan samples show lower adsorption capacities. This was unexpected at first, but when the micropore volume for the different samples is examined, it can be observed that there has been a sharp decrease of micropore volume due to the activation process. The acid washing process seems to somewhat improve the micropore volume values but only in a minor way. Pore size distributions for the KOH-treated carbon black samples are shown in Fig. 2. Y. Takasu et al. [22] reported that the pore size distribution of Vulcan XC-72R revealed at weak peak around 3 nm and a broad peak around 40-70 nm with a maximum pore volume of 0.35 cm³ g⁻¹ at about 40 nm. The activated Vulcan samples show similar pore size distributions up to about 20 nm but change dramatically for the bigger mesopores, where the maximum shifts to bigger pore sizes and instead of one broad peak two distinct peaks with much higher pore volumes. Here it can be clearly seen the effect of the washing process on the higher mesopore structure of the treated carbons, especially in the case of VKN where it can be seen an increase of both the pore sizes and the pore volume. From all this, it can be concluded that the activation has broadened the porosity of the Vulcan carbon, destroying the existent microporosity while creating bigger mesopores.

Fig. 2 BJH method mesopore size distribution curves of the activated Vulcan carbon black supports: V (— · —), VKOH (dark solid line), VKCl (— — —) and VKN (— — —).

The morphology of the Vulcan samples was studied by SEM. SEM micrographs of the Vulcan samples before and after activation are shown in Fig. 3. It was found that, in the case of untreated Vulcan (Fig. 3a) it is a material that is not monodispersed and its pore structure seems to arise from the free space in the particle aggregates that form the material. In the case of the activated Vulcan samples, for VKOH (Fig. 3b) bigger pores start to show but the difference is more noticeable for VKCl and VKN (Fig. 3c and d, respectively) where it can be seen that the spacing between aggregates increases, together with the amount of spaces, giving the structure a more “open” morphology.

EDX analysis was done at the same time as the SEM analysis and it was found that there were no changes in the chemical composition of the carbons and that neither the activating agents nor the acid washing process did add any impurities to the KOH treated carbon, as no noticeable amounts of K nor Cl or N were seen on the washed samples.

Fig. 3 SEM micrographs of Vulcan XC-72R carbon black supports before and after activation: (a) untreated Vulcan, (b) VKOH, (c) VKCl, (d) VKN.

3.2. Fuel cell measurement

In this study, performance of MEAs fabricated with NiNbPtRu anode catalyst with different carbon supports and Nafion 115 membrane were assessed in a home-made PEM single fuel cell. The electrocatalyst tested as anode was $\text{Ni}_{59}\text{Nb}_{40}\text{Pt}_{0.6}\text{Ru}_{0.4}$ [23-25]. As this new catalyst has a monophasic amorphous structure, it is possible to obtain homogeneous distributions of Pt, which improves its behavior with much lesser amounts of Pt compared with polycrystalline alloys. Different electrodes are prepared adopting different carbons in this blend. A commercial Pt/C was used as the cathode. Fig. 4 shows the mass activity ($\text{A g}^{-1}\text{Pt}$) and mass power ($\text{W g}^{-1}\text{Pt}$) curves obtained when the treated carbon samples supporting the $\text{Ni}_{59}\text{Nb}_{40}\text{Pt}_{0.6}\text{Ru}_{0.4}$ as anode electro-catalyst were tested.

Table 2 details the main data obtained in these experiments. It can be observed that the poorest results come from the use of unactivated Vulcan. Comparing the results obtained for sample V with the ones for the commercial Glassy Carbon (CV) it can be seen that they are 10 times lower for sample V.

Table 2 Summary of experimental bench measurements for MEAs fabricated with Nafion 115 and sprayed with inks made out of different carbon supports.

Sample	Maximum power mW	j mA/cm ²	Potential V	Mass activity A/g Pt	Mass power W/g Pt
CV	94.10	22.22	0.47	2155.17	1014.01
V	8.60	2.01	0.48	195.46	92.65
VKOH	15.10	2.67	0.61	258.62	162.72
VKCl	49.73	7.69	0.65	745.69	535.88
VKN	82.10	18.99	0.48	1841.60	884.70

Looking at the variations in the behavior of the MEA when using the different Vulcan carbon blacks activated with KOH, a general improvement in the behavior of the support is observed. This improvement is even more noticeable when the activated samples have been washed with acid solutions, VKCl and VKN. For all the Vulcan samples, maximum values of mass activity and mass power were obtained with MEAs that used VKN as catalyst support.

Fig. 4 Performance of MEAs fabricated with different catalyst supports in a home made PEM single fuel cell. The electro-catalyst used was Ni₅₉Nb₄₀Pt_{0.6}Ru_{0.4} and the membrane was Nafion 115, (a) Potential vs Intensity vs Power, (b) Potential vs Mass Activity vs Mass Power.

The aim of the washing process is to remove the possible alkaline compounds present in the activated carbon after chemical activation. There are two reasons to do this: first, to remove impurities and possible corrosion problems derived from the presence of alkaline compounds and, the second, to eliminate compounds that might be blocking the access to the porosity that has been created during activation. Previous studies on chemical activation of other carbon supports [16] observed that while water seems to remove most of KOH, washing the samples with a HCl solution made a more thorough

job removing potassium compounds formed during the activation reaction, that translated into a better accessibility to the porosity which would explain its better performance.

To try to explain the much better performance of the sample washed with HNO₃ (VKN) compared with the one washed with HCl (VKCl), at first it was thought that as nitric acid is a typical reactive used for functionalization of carbon supports [26e28], some light surface modification could have occurred that would improve the performance on VKN. To try to prove this, FTIR studies were made on the Vulcan samples (data not shown) that refuted the theory as no discernible changes were discovered in the surface chemistry of the samples. In light of this, it is reasonable to think the main reason for the property improvements of the support are purely due to the pore structure modification as a result of the combination of its activation with KOH and following washing with HNO₃.

4. Conclusions

The influence of the washing method of the Vulcan samples after activation with KOH brings big changes in the behavior of the supports in MEAs. This effect seems to be particularly true in the case of the sample washed with the HNO₃ solution (VKN) there can be observed results close to the one for the commercial Glassy Carbon. While there seem to be no noticeable differences in the surface chemistry (FTIR) of the different supports nor in the chemical composition (EDX) of the samples, it has been observed a decrease in microporosity and an increase on the mesoporosity in the Vulcan XC-72R carbon black samples due to the chemical activation treatment. The subsequent acid washing process has improved the accessibility to the bigger pores. This increase of the amount and size of bigger pores in VKN might have favored the gas flow easing the access of hydrogen to the catalytic surface, increasing its catalytic activity.

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r e f e r e n c e s

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